

06/05 Mon		
07/05 Tue	IT Maintenance at PhyLife (see below)	All PhyLife
08/05 Wed		
09/05 Thu	Ascension Day - SDU closed	
10/05 Fri		

Arrangementer / Upcoming events: [Webkalender](#)

Highlights

FKF Activity Day / Maintenance of IT at PhyLife / FKF student on the winning team of physics tournament / Educational news / Minutes from NAT-FAK / Workshop on AI for Researchers

Nyt fra instituttet / News from the department

Du kan altid se flere nyheder og arrangementer på instituttets sider på [SDU.net](#). / You can always find more news and events in the calendar at the department pages at [SDU.net](#).

Next FKF Activity Day coming up May 17 at 14.00:

Activity topic: Drawing and painting

FKF ACTIVITY DAYS

FOR EVERYONE AT FKF!

Date: 17/5-24 14.00-15.00

Activity: Frederik and Lilian are doing a "show and tell" about drawing and painting. So, if you are interested in getting started or have questions about this topic come and join us. There will be coffee and cake.

Where? Riddersalen

Contacts: Christian (christianbj@sdu.dk)
Emma: (emms@sdu.dk)

Vedligehold af IT med påvirkning af ventilation på PhyLife 7. maj / Maintenance of IT with impact on ventilation at PhyLife May 7th

IT:

Opgradering af aktivt netværksudstyr i dele af bygning 28A (PhyLife) d. 7. maj.

Der vil være netværks afbrydelser i løbet af dagen (8.00-15.00)

Ventilation:

Arbejdet nævnt ovenfor kan medføre stop af ventilation i laboratorier herunder stinkskabe i tidsrummet kl. 08.00 - 09.30, så det bør der tages forholdsregler for.

IT:

Upgrade of active network equipment in parts of building 28A (PhyLife) on May 7th.

There will be network interruptions during the day (8.00-15.00)

Ventilation:

The work mentioned above may cause ventilation in laboratories, including fume hoods, to stop during the period between 08.00 - 09.30, so precautions should be taken for that.

FKF Physics student on the winner team in Zürich

FKF would like to congratulate Lisanne Zoe Löher for her self-motivated participation and extraordinary achievements at the 16th International Physics Tournament 2024 (<https://iptnet.info/>) held in Zürich (Switzerland) during 2. - 6. April 2024.

Lisanne is an enrolled SDU master student in physics and formed part of the tournaments overall winning team representing Germany. During her preparatory work, in addition to her normal study duties at SDU, she received financial support and mentoring advice from FKF / SDU-Galaxy.

For 2024 / 2025 Lisanne will try and participate in FKF's physics outreach activities and talk about her experience in participating in an international physics competition. We hope that this effort will inspire current and future SDU / FKF physics students to contribute with a project for the 2025 or 2026 IPT tournament. Thank you, Lisanne - a hearty congratulation -- we wish you all the best for your future career!

Tobias C. Hinse & Mads T. Frandsen

Nyheder fra uddannelsesområdet - særligt for studerende / News about educationalsubjects - especially for students

I denne nyhed fra [Servicesiden Undervisning](#) på SDU.net kan du læse om 5 succeser fra hverdagen: Dialogforum, udlandsophold, SDU's kvalitetssystem, SDU Takeover og uniTEST. Alle nyheder, hvor studerende har spillet en rolle eller har hente gode erfaringer.

In [this news from the Teaching Services page](#) on SDU.net, you can read about 5 successes from everyday life: *Dialog forum, study abroad, SDU's quality system, SDU Takeover and uniTEST.* All news where students have played a role or can gain good experience.

Møder / Meetings

[Dagsordner og referater fra møder på FKF](#) (Agendas and minutes from FKF meetings. Some might only be in Danish)

Referat fra NAT-FAK ledelsesmøde / Minutes from NAT-FAK Management

I [referat fra møde i fakultetsledelsen den 16. april](#) kan I læse om:

- **Dekansekretariatet i FAKSEK:** Teamleder Mikkel L. Johansson deltog med en afrapportering af dekansekretariatet i FAKSEK.
- **Valg til arbejdsmiljøorganisationen:** Fakultetsledelsen drøftede omorganiseringen på arbejdsmiljøområdet, inden der afholdes valg i juni '24.
- **Strategi 2021-2025: Infrastruktur:** Fakultetsledelsen fulgte op på punkt om infrastruktur på uddannelsesområdet, som var til drøftelse på fakultetsledelsesmødet den 2. april.

I [referat fra møde i fakultetsledelsen den 2. april](#) kan I læse om:

- **SDU ESscience-center:** Professor Claudio Pica deltog i ledelsesmødet, hvor han gav en status på SDU ESscience-center.
- **Strategi 2021-2025: Infrastruktur:** Frants R. Lauritsen deltog i ledelsesmødet, hvor han præsenterede den tilbagemelding, som NAT-FAKs Infrastrukturudvalg for uddannelse var kommet med til fakultetsledelsen.
- **Forventningsafstemning i forskningsmiljøer:** Professor Amelia-Elena Rotaru deltog i ledelsesmødet til en dialog om et forventningsafstemningsdokument, som hun har udarbejdet sammen med sin forskningsgruppe.

In [the minutes from the Faculty Management meeting on April 16](#) (Danish only), you can read about:

- **Dean's Office at Faculty Administration:** Team leader Mikkel L. Johansson participated with a report from the Dean's Office at the Faculty Administration.
- **Electtion for the Occupational Health and Safety Organization:** The faculty management discussed the organization of occupational health and safety before the elections in June '24.
- **Strategy 2021-2025: Infrastructure:** The faculty management followed up on the point regarding infrastructure in the education area, which was discussed during the faculty leadership meeting on April 2nd.

In [the minutes from the Faculty Management meeting on April 2](#) (Danish only), you can read about:

- **SDU ESscience Center:** Professor Claudio Pica participated in the management meeting where he provided a status update on the SDU ESscience Center.
- **Strategy 2021-2025: Infrastructure:** Frants R. Lauritsen attended the management meeting where he presented the feedback that the NAT-FAK's Infrastructure Committee for Education had provided to the faculty management.
- **Expectation Alignment in Research Environments:** Professor Amelia-Elena Rotaru participated in the management meeting for a dialogue about an expectation alignment document that she has developed together with her research group.

Ledige stillinger på FKF / Positions at FKF

Alle ledige stillinger (bl.a. instruktører og studentermedhjælpere) på NAT kan ses [HER](#). / All positions (incl. instructors and adm. assistants) can be seen [HERE](#).

[Assistant/Associate/Full Professor \(tenured\) in Pharmaceutics](#) (FKF): 15.05.2024

Gæsteforsker / Guest Researcher

Guest Researcher Stav Zalel, 05.05.2024-11.05.2024

Research group: Astrid Eichhorn

Guest Researcher Behnam Mohammadi, 01.05.2024-31.10.2024

Research group: Himanshu Khandelua

Ny titel / New titeI

Assistant professor Tobias Cornelius Hinse, 01.04.2024-31.03.2027

Research group: Mads T. Frandsen (external funding for outreach)

Opslagstavlen / Noticeboard

Workshop on AI for researchers by Avidnote

This is an announcement about an upcoming online workshop for researchers from Danish universities, **Fri 10th of May at 10:00**, on the topic: [Practical Workshop on using AI for researchers](#)

It is a follow-up to the previous seminar and covers new features in AI tools for researchers.

- # New tips and strategies for using AI in research, focusing on writing.
- # Using AI for data analysis, writing and reading
- # The latest guideline for researchers working in the EU

To register: <https://events.teams.microsoft.com/event/2d6f7b9f-d6e5-4525-8b70-88ddb401542@22922e78-c07a-462d-a26d-31a0393a1538>

You are welcome to share the invitation with colleagues. For questions, please reply to this message.

With best regards,
Aberisak Adam, PhD
Research coordinator, Avidnote

Om KIK: Indlæg sendes til: kik@sdu.dk. Modtagere: alle på distributionslisten DL-NAT-FKF-everyone. KIK kan ses online her: <https://syddanskuni.sharepoint.com/sites/ifk/KIK/Forms/AllItems.aspx>